

Minutes EB25-2
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
21 May 2025 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apologies

Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Training video
ISME Communications

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.*
Completed
- PH to request the ISME Board to reconsider the requirement that ISME funding cannot be used for the payment of persons assisting with the development of the Registry.*
The ISME executive director indicated that funding cannot be used to pay salaries. Previous funding was granted as it was considered to be a stipend to a student. PH will ask if future funding could again be used as a stipend. The ISME office indicated that they would be willing to coordinate and administer the SeqCode prize in future. PH to communicate to ISME that we are grateful for this arrangement.
- FV to draft a text for a Wikipedia article on the SeqCode and circulated it amongst the EB.*
Text has been drafted with the help of ChatGPT. It will now be circulated amongst the EB.
- BW to prepare a draft proposal for possible amendments to the code to include paratypes for further discussion by the EB.*
Ongoing, could be added to future proposals to amend the SeqCode.
- KK, IS, MC and LMR to prepare interim reports from the commissions or working groups to be submitted on 15 March 2025.*
Report to ISME has been finalised and circulated. FV will now submit it to ISME.
- KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding with BW and ALR as co-PIs.*

This will not be pursued for the time being as the funding landscape in the US has changed dramatically.

7. *KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.*
Ongoing.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

Nothing to report.

Standards Working Group

The working group will still meet to discuss the possibility of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries of genome sequences. It was also suggested that the working group examine the need to specify quality requirements for genomes obtained from isolates.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 850 names have been validated which include those of 436 species.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission had a meeting to discuss issues related to the priority of names of higher taxa and the validation of *Candidatus* names for higher taxa. It was decided that no action will be taken as these names have protection until 1 January 2027 according to Rule 23 d.

5. Dialog between the ICSP, BISMIS and the SeqCode

We were informed that the ICNP did not accept the invitation to participate in such a dialog at present but could consider such a discussion at a later stage, such as the next IUMS meeting in Portugal (2026). However, they are open to initial discussions to form an organizing committee and prepare the agenda for such a meeting.

6. Preparation of the annual report for ISME

The report to ISME has been finalised and circulated. FV will now submit it to ISME and post on Zenodo.

7. Recording of SeqCode names in NCBI

NCBI indicated that they will wait to see how the new Section 10 rules will be implemented before deciding on how they will deal with names validated under the SeqCode. Only names published in *Candidatus* lists will receive pre-validation status. Requests for names to be added to future *Candidatus* lists will have to be submitted to the IJSEM according to the requirements indicated on their website. The EB strongly feels that we should continue to encourage the use of the SeqCode and should not make a special effort to ensure that SeqCode names appear on the Candidatus Lists.

8. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

MC reported on her presentation at the Westerdijk Spring Symposium “DNA Sequences as Type” held on 7 – 8 April where different options of implementing sequence data as type material were discussed by prominent mycology taxonomists.

9. Training video

LMR has prepared a training video for the SeqCode community which consists of two parts. The first part is a brief introduction to the SeqCode presented by LMR. The second part presented by Dominik Berrens from the University of Mainz is a primer in Latin for Prokaryotic Nomenclature. The EB congratulated LMR on the video but requested for it to be split into two separate videos. Links to these videos will now be shared widely on social media.

10. ISME Communications

In recognition of the vital role that naming and classification play in ecological studies, ISME Communications has expanded its scope to include ecology papers that address taxonomy and nomenclature. To assist with these manuscripts MV, FV, and Marike Palmer have joined the ISME Communications Editorial Board as Senior Editors.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. PH to inform ISME that we are grateful that they will take over the administration of the SeqCode prize
3. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to consider specifying quality requirements for genomes obtained from isolates.
4. LMR to split the training video into two and the links to be shared with the wider community.

Ongoing action items

5. PH to request the ISME Board to allow ISME funding to be used as stipends to students.
6. FV to circulate the draft text for a Wikipedia article on the SeqCode amongst the EB.
7. BW to investigate possible amendments to the code such as including paratypes.
8. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.

Minutes prepared by FV: 4 June 2025

Approved: 9 June 2025